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Scholarly Communications Professional

MINIMUM VIABLE SKILLS PROFILE

- Skills for the European
- Open Science
- Commons

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Scholarly Communications Professional

Minimum Viable Skills Profile

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Disclaimer

This booklet is part of the **Skills4EOSC collection of Minimum Viable Skills Profiles (MVS)**, which outline key Open Science competencies for different professional roles. It presents a focused extract from the **Annex to Deliverable D2.6**, designed to support usability and communication. To explore the full list of profiles, visit the Skills4EOSC website (<https://www.skills4eosC.eu/resources/publications/mvs>) or consult the full Annex (<https://zenodo.org/records/15761916>).

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics	MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement	ORCC	Open Research Competencies Coalition
DMP	Data Management Plan	OS	Open Science
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues	R&I	Research and Innovation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud	RDA	Research Data Alliance
ETHRD IG	Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group (RDA)	RDM	Research Data Management
ICT	Information and Communication Technology	RI	Research Infrastructure
IT	Information Technology	RPO	Research Performing Organisation
JRC	Joint Research Centre	RSE	Research Software Engineer
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	T4fs	Terms for FAIR skills

1. Introduction

| Open Science mission for this role

According to UNESCO, “**Scholarly communication** is the process of sharing, disseminating and publishing research findings of academics and researchers so that the generated academic contents are made available to the global academic communities”¹.

The Minimum Viable Skillset for Scholarly Communication Professionals describes the Open Science and Data Management skills required for those roles contributing to the creation, curation, and dissemination of scholarly outputs, with a particular attention to publications.

Publications and scholarly outputs in general are not only the result of scientific activities, but a component of the open science ecosystem and therefore requiring the same OS and RDM skills as other OS products.

¹ <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000231938>.

SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION PROFESSIONAL

The Scholarly Communication Professional (SCP) deals with Scholarly Communication Artifacts, which entail, but are not limited to: articles, books, posts, annotations. SCPs engaged in Open Science ensure open access to the Scholarly Communication Artifacts, and more broadly their full integration into the OS environment. SCPs not only apply OS and RDM principles to the traditional and innovative forms of Scholarly Communication Artifacts, but they also address OS aspects beyond RDM best practices.

In that prospect, the SCP designs and/or implements OS policies and recommendations and applies methods and standards to ensure high-quality, accessible and reproducible research outputs.

ASSOCIATED FUNCTION TITLES:

Publisher, Editor, Librarian

ORGANISATIONAL CONTEXT:

Libraries, Research Performing Organizations (learned societies, universities, research centres), Scientific publishers, Research Infrastructures

ESSENTIAL SKILLS FOR THIS ROLE

- Expertise in data literacy both as a practitioner and a trainer.
- Knowledge of repositories and aggregator types, scope, and requirements.
- Knowledge of open publication models (green, gold, diamond).
- Ability to generate and understand bibliometrics, altmetrics, and usage metrics.
- Ability to apply FAIR principles to a variety of scholarly outputs, including expertise in persistent identification of contents, standard metadata generation and storage, and good knowledge of discipline-specific output types and standards.
- Knowledge about Linked Open Data and semantic interoperability.
- Knowledge about legal aspects related to IP/copyright/privacy, as well as data protection for sensitive data and information. Includes the ability to balance data protection requirements with open science/FAIR principles.
- Knowledge and ability to apply Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and the CARE (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics) principles.
- Ability to design, organize, and manage physical and digital trainings and events.

SOFT / TRANSVERSAL SKILLS

Considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Team management and project management, for results-oriented planning and organisation.
- Stakeholder engagement and networking to translate and bridge needs.
- Creativity, curiosity and openness with a willingness to learn.
- Critical and analytical thinking.
- Conflict management and mediation, with a patient, empathic approach.

BACKGROUND ASSUMPTIONS

MAIN ACTIVITIES

- Maintains and/or uses a publishing platform or a repository providing interoperable contents.
- Guides and supports users in disseminating standardized and FAIRified scholarly communication artifacts.
- Guides and supports users in enhancing their data literacy skills and working effectively with various types of data.
- Negotiates with publishers for open access publishing.
- Curates and enriches the data to ensure semantic and technical interoperability with a range of aggregators' specifications.
- Uses tools and follows procedures to achieve sustainability of published resources.
- Ensures compliance of published output with ethical and legal recommendations.
- Organises and monitors processes of content creation, review and dissemination.
- Integrates the aspects of diversity, inclusiveness and integrity in the process of information sharing.
- Participates and contributes to trans-professional networks including librarians, publishers, IT experts, legal experts, etc.

CONTRIBUTES TO WHICH OPEN SCIENCE OUTCOMES?

The SCP manages Scholarly Communication Artifacts as research data, following OS and RDM principles, including the FAIR principles, both for the contents (e.g. using interoperable standard structured formats), and for their metadata (e.g., using PIDs and standard metadata schemas). The SCP ensures this way that Scholarly Communication Artifacts are not only disseminated as research results but made available as reusable research data.

LIBER (Association of European Research Libraries) identifies the following contributions to OS proper to librarians that also characterize any SCP's activity:

- Scholarly Communication Artifacts are accessible as research data, with relevant metrics, following OS and RDM principles.

Research integrity is enhanced by applying FAIR principles both to artifact contents e.g. using interoperable standard structured formats, and to their metadata e.g. using PIDs and standard metadata schemas.

Further information

OPEN SCIENCE SKILLS TERMS

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Develop professional network with researchers and scientists](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Manage open publications](#); [Manage research data](#); [Operate open-source software](#); [Perform project management](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Teach in academic or vocational contexts](#); [Think abstractly](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Advise others](#); [Apply basic programming skills](#); [Apply digital security measures](#); [Apply knowledge of science, technology and engineering](#); [Build networks](#); [Comply with regulations](#); [Demonstrate willingness to learn](#); [Instruct others](#); [Manage quality](#); [Manage time](#); [Organize information, objects and resources](#); [Plan](#); [Promote ideas, products, services](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Respect the diversity of cultural values and norms](#); [Show empathy](#); [Show initiative](#); [Solve problems](#); [Think analytically](#); [Think creatively](#); [Think critically](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Work in teams](#).

ResearchComp: [Abstract thinking](#); [Interact professionally](#); [Mobilise resources](#); [Negotiate](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#).

Terms4FAIRskills: Assessment on FAIR data criteria; Community building; Data access risk assessment and mitigation; Data archiving; Data categorisation; Data curation; Data governance; Data policy; Data quality assessment & review; Digital archiving; Evaluating repositories for data deposit/sharing; Information security; Knowledge to contextualize FAIR principles to domain; Meeting/conference organization; Mentoring on open and FAIR methods; Metadata creation; Metadata exposure; Preservation; Privacy governance; Training in open and FAIR methods; User acceptance testing.

CSCCE: Advocacy; Collaboration; Community governance; Consultation and listening; Cultural competence; Engagement; Event planning; Knowledge brokering; Landscape analysis; Media production; Meeting facilitation; Moderation, mediation and intervention; Networking; Operational planning and implementation; Outreach; Record-keeping; Speaking and presenting; Teaching and training.

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